
Role of Open Access E- Resources in Libraries: With Special Reference to Changing Environment

Mr. Meshram Rajesh Martand

Librarian,

Shri Yashwantrao Patil Science College, Solankur.

Tal. Radhanagari, Dist. Kolhapur.

Corresponding Author –Mr. Meshram Rajesh Martand

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Abstract:

The 21st century is known as a knowledge society. In the 21st century, new trends in technology are being developed. This has led to a huge change in the social scenario. Significant changes have occurred in social, economic, educational, and political views.

ICT has changed the nature of academic libraries. A variety of terms such as hybrid, digital, and virtual library are used to refer to the modern academic library. The pace of change brought about by new information technologies has a key impact on the way people live. In today's world, electronically formatted, open-access resources have become very popular. Today, academic libraries are increasingly using e-resources. Open Access literature is digital, free of charge, and free of most copyright and licensing restrictions. The benefits of open access appear to be mutually beneficial to all participants in the scholarly communication process.

This paper is a literature review on the role and use of open-access e-resources in academic libraries.

Keywords: *Open Access, e-journal, e-book, consortia, digital libraries, etc.*

Introduction:

The development of information and communication technology (ICT), the mode of access to scholarly information has changed from print to electronic. The concept of e-journals consortia emerged as a subscription model to journals during the time due to the high cost of access to e journals. In parallel with this technological development the amount of research itself has increased exponentially, coupled with the desire for wider dissemination of research result. From this situation, open access has emerged as a business model for scholarly journals as an alternative to subscription and has attracted considerable attention in recent years.

Open Access movement is a worldwide phenomenon to mitigate challenges faced by the global libraries and

research institutions related to 'serials crisis' - a spiraling effect of constant increase in subscription cost of many scholarly journals and exponential hike of online access fees of journals in 1990s that led to cancellation or reduction of subscriptions of many ever priced serials due to budgetary limits. Open Access initiatives have tried to provide initially Gratis Open Access and later Libre Open Access to scholarly literature. The first ever formal Open Access repository launched was the arXiv.org in 1991 which helped researchers in self-archiving of their electronic preprints of scientific papers in the fields of physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance and statistics. Many stakeholders came forward in building institutions and resources for shaping up the global open

access movements. Some of the institutions emerged during this decade are namely, Public Library of Science (PLOS), BioMed Central (BMC) - publishers of peer-reviewed Open Access journals, the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition (SPARC), and Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA). Most importantly, the Budapest, Berlin and Bethesda (BBB) Open Access declarations or statements got signed by the scholarly communities, particularly by the funding agencies, research councils, learned societies, institutions, universities, and scientists for the Open Access dissemination of public funded research.

What is Open Access?

According to BOAI the concept of Open Access refers to "[the] free availability on the public internet, permitting any users

to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself" (BOAI, 2002).

The Bethesda Statement (2003) defines open access, where "The author(s) and copyright holder(s) grant(s) to all users a free, irrevocable, worldwide, perpetual right of access to, and a license to copy, use, distribute, transmit and display the work publicly and to make and distribute derivative works, in any digital medium for any responsible purpose, subject to proper attribution of authorship as well as the right to make small numbers of printed copies for their personal use".

Characteristics of Open Access E-Resources

- It is free availability of scholarly publication.
- It is free of copyright and licensing restrictions. Materials are available online or on the internet.
- Material is full text. Material can be accessed by anybody from anywhere without any discrimination.
- Open Access contents can be in any format from texts and data to software,

audio, video, and multi-media, scholarly articles and their preprints.

- You can access digital information 24/7
- Anywhere, any time...
- No need to visit the library
- Information can be cut or copied & pasted from one document to another every easily
- Digital information may be free or cheaper than print equivalents.
- Digital information can be sent in multiple copies simultaneously over

information's networks in fractions of a minute or even of a second.

➤ Saved the space of Library.

Open Access E-Resources:

There are some popular Open Access Resources websites-

Sr. No	Name	Doman
E-Books :		
1	DOAB: Directory of Books 7135 Books available	http://doabooks.org
2	PDF drive	http://pdfdrive.net
3	ebooks@Adelaide	https://ebooks.adelaide.edu.au
4	OAPEN	http://www.oapen.org/home
5	Open Library	https://openlibrary.org
6	In Tech open Books	www.intechopen.com/books
7	Rare Book	www.rarebookroom.org
8	The Universal Digital Library Million Book Collection	www.ulib.org/index.html
9	Read Print	www.readprint.com
10	National Digital library of India (19,845,301 books)	https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/
11	Bhandarkar Oriental Research (BORI) 1001 Rare Digital Books	http://borilib.com/repository
E-Journals :		
1	DOAJ-Directory of open access Journals	http://doaj.org
2	Open access Directory	http://oad.simmons.edu/oadewiki/main_page
3	Open DOAR	https://opendoar.org
4	ROAR	http://roarmap.eprints.org
5	ROAD	https://road.issn.org
6	Peer J	www.peerj.com
7	Med know Journals	www.medknow.com
8	Indian Society for Education & Environment	www.iseeadyar.org/index.html
9	Biomed Central (STM)	https://www.biomedcentral.com/journals
10	Springer Open	https://www.springeropen.com/
11	Science & Education Publishing (SciEP)	http://www.sciepub.com/portal/Home
Theses & Dissertation :		
1	ShodhGanga - UGC & INFLIBNET, India	http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in
2	NDTLD	http://www.ndltd.org
3	Open Access Theses & Dissertation : OATD	https://oatd.org
4	Open Directory Project Free Dissertation	http://dmoz.org/search?q=free+dissertation
5	Open Thesis.org	http://www.openthesis.org
6	PQDT OPEN : Pro Quest Digital Theses	http://www.pqdtopen.proquest.com
7	Mahatma Gandhi University online Theses Library	http://www.mgutheses.in

Benefit of Open Access E resources:

There are number of benefit of electronic resources such.

1. Saves costs of students.
2. Grants access to more quality choices.
3. Help to teaching and learning process.
4. Provides peace of mind for all users.
5. Provides quality guarantee.
6. Allows remote access.
7. It can be used by many users simultaneously.
8. Provides timely access to documents.
9. Supports searching Capabilities.
10. Accommodates unique features such as links to related items.
11. Eliminates printing and postage cost.
12. It can easily merge with altering services.
13. It does not require physical Processing.

Special Features of E-Resources:

E-resources have some distant features which differentiate them from traditional resources. E-resources on the Internet are further distinct by the nature of the information on the net itself. The features of 21st century information and media are_

1. High compact storage.
2. Ease of reproduction, multiplication and manipulation and transmutation;
3. Contents can be very easily detaches from its media or container,
4. Hypertext and multimedia;
5. Ease of migration of contents from one medium to another,
6. Ease of transmission, communication and storage;
7. Seamless integration of print and electronic resources;
8. Sophisticated and multipronged searches through keywords, free text, Boolean operators, lass numbers and natural languages processing.

ICT base E-resources and changing environment in Libraries:

Information and communication technology has become essential part of 21st century's libraries. ICT has made drastic change in the field of libraries, the libraries has transformed from traditional libraries to digital libraries or hybrid libraries. Therefore the librarians must create technological environment to make sense of a multiplicity of digital collections and resources. They must identify strategies to provide access to wide range of networks & information resources. For this purpose they need new skills to manage and create many information sources and services. The competencies & skills form the basis for the continued survival and growth of professional in the new information technology age. So in the fast changing environment, the library professional must possess multi skills, multi-tasking abilities and competent in specialized area of work.

Conclusion:

Open access supported by information technology has become a public movement globally and this movement has provided new challenges as well as opportunities for the librarians. The libraries are implementing ICT based library services and librarians managing digital library and hybrid library, institutional repositories publishing maintaining open access E-journals, E-books and developing web portal. Open access provides a new paradigm for libraries and librarians. It provides opportunities for library professionals to deliver qualitative and quantitative content in to the users.

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